

Supplementary information for manuscript

Development of high-performance and cost-effective electrode assembly for redox flow battery

Přemysl Ríchnr^a, Tobias Gerber^b, Peter Fischer^b, Jiří Charvát^c, Christian Röss^d, Jens Noack^b, Björn Hage^e, Miloš Svoboda^f, David Gráf^a, Jan Beneš^f, Petr Mazúr^a

^aUniversity of Chemistry and Technology Prague, Department of Chemical Engineering, Technická 5, 166 28 Prague, Czech Republic

^bFraunhofer Institute for Chemical Technology ICT, Department of Applied Electrochemistry, Joseph-von-Fraunhofer-Straße 7, 76327 Pfinztal, Germany

^cPinflow energy storage, s.r.o. – Křižovnická 86/6, 110 00 Prague, Czech Republic

^dFraunhofer Institute for Chemical Technology ICT, Department of Polymer Engineering, Joseph-von-Fraunhofer-Straße 7, 76327 Pfinztal, Germany

^eBH Consulting Ltd., 4A Richardsson Rd, Coogee, WA, 6166 Australia

^fNew Technologies – Research Centre, University of West Bohemia, Univerzitní 8, 306 14, Plzeň, Czech Republic

Figure S1: a) Position of thermocouples in GF/BP/GF electrode assembly z-x view and in b) y-x view.

Figure S2: Scheme of apparatus for dry resistance measurement: 1) pistons of press, 2) PP insulation plates, 3) composite plates, 4) GF/BP/GF electrode assembly.

a)

b)

Figure S3: Scheme of assemblies for dry resistance measurement and positioning of voltage and current sensing for each arrangement: **a)** GF/BP_{ext.} arrangement, **b)** GF/BP_{ext.}/GF arrangement, **c)** CC/BP_{ext.}/GF arrangement. The sing plus (+) stand for unbonded components, and the dark red line represent position of connection.

b)

c)

Figure S4: a) Schematics of VRFB single cell. b) Schematics of experimental set-up for testing electrode assemblies consisting of VRFB single cell, OCV cell, tubing, diaphragm pumps and tanks (green dash line represents membrane). c) Schematics of experimental for testing electrode assemblies set-up consisting of VRFB stack, OCV cell, tubing, peristaltic pumps and tanks.

Fig. S5. Scheme of equivalent circuit for evaluation of R_{Ω} and R_{CT} from EIS spectra. $R_{CT} = R_{CT1} + R_{CT2}$. EC-lab fitting tool was used for fitting the EIS spectra. In manuscript all resistances are multiplied by geometric area of electrode (i.e. 50 cm^2) and thus referred to as area specific resistance (*ASR*).

Figure S6: Photos of hot-press welded GF/BP electrode assemblies illustrating effect of too high temperature resulting in over melting of BP: **a)** top site, **b)** bottom side. The figure b also represents decreased area in GF/BP_{ext.} connection. **c)** Additional photography of damage caused by insufficient length of cooling phase, i.e. elevated area in GF/BP connection. **d)** Half-cut through GF/BP_{ext.} electrode assembly shows effective bonding of GF. **e)** and **f)** Fibers of GF remaining in the structure of BP after ripping off the GF from GF/BP electrode assembly.

a)

b)

Figure S7: Photos of copper current collector welding to BP showing: **a)** manually disconnected Cu plate from BP after hot-press welding under non-optimal conditions illustrating non-ideal component connection (red arrow shows the area of the oxidized copper surface where the CC has been ripped off the BP due to excessive stress). **b)** CC/BP_{ext.}/GF electrode assembly with Cu foil effectively connected: left picture shows CC/BP_{ext.}/GF with cleaned Cu foil after connection, right picture shows the oxidation of Cu foil surface that occurs in air atmosphere at elevated temperatures. Prior to the welding, all the CCs were cleaned and looked as on the left picture.

Table S1: Dry area specific resistances of RFB single-cell without membrane evaluated from load curve measurement.

Single-cell	$ASR_{dry-cell} / \Omega \text{ cm}^2$	CR / %
GF+BP _{com.}	0.52	20
GF+BP _{ext.}	2.1	20
GF/BP _{ext.}	0.86	10
CC/BP _{ext.} /GF	0.52	10

Figure S8: Area specific resistances of the VRFB single-cell with GF₁: **a)** ASR_{Ω} in -50% and +50% SoC evaluated from EIS at the beginning (INT) and after cycling (AFT). **b)** ASR_{LC} in +50% SoC evaluated from load curves (charge and discharge). **Working conditions:** 1.6 mol dm⁻³ vanadium electrolyte, room temperature, 75 ml min⁻¹. Load curve measurement current density range 0 – 60 mA cm⁻².

Table S2: Comparison of mean efficiencies and capacity utilization for VRFB single-cell experiments.

	CE / %	EE / %	CU / %
CC/BP _{ext.} /GF	98.2	87.7	78.8
CC/BP _{ext.} /GF (repeat)	98.3	85.7	78.2
GF/BP _{ext.}	98.0	84.6	79.1
GF/BP _{ext.} (repeat)	98.0	83.9	79.7

Figure S9: Area specific resistances of the VRFB single-cell with GF₂ comparing two different bonding methods: **a)** ASR_{Ω} in -50% and +50% SoC evaluated from EIS at the beginning (INT) and after cycling (AFT). **b)** ASR_{LC} in +50% SoC evaluated from load curves (charge and discharge). **Working conditions:** 1.6 mol dm⁻³ vanadium electrolyte, room temperature, 75 ml min⁻¹. Load curve measurement current density range 0 – 60 mA cm⁻².

Figure S10: Area specific resistances of the VRFB stack (per a single cell): **a)** ASR_{LC} in +50% SoC evaluated from load curve measurements at the beginning (INT) and after cycling (AFT). **b)** ASR_{Ω} , ASR_{CT} , $ASR_{EIS\text{-tot}}$ in +50% SoC evaluated from EIS. **Working conditions:** 1.6 mol dm⁻³ vanadium electrolyte, room temperature, 150 ml min⁻¹. Load curve measurement current density range 0 – 60 mA cm⁻².

Figure S11: Summary of VRFB stack long-term experiment results: **a)** Development of efficiencies and capacity utilization during the long-term cycling. **b)** Evolution of EIS spectra (in +50 % SoC) during the long-term experiment (always after electrolyte remixing or exchange). **Working conditions:** 1.6 mol dm⁻³ vanadium electrolyte, 20 °C, 150 ml min⁻¹, charge/discharge current density 80 mA cm⁻², voltage limits 1.6 V – 3.5 V.

Table S3: Evaluated area specific resistances of VRFB stack (per individual cell) over long-term cycling experiment.

	ASR_{Ω}	ASR_{CT}	$ASR_{EIS-tot}$
	$\Omega \text{ cm}^2$	$\Omega \text{ cm}^2$	$\Omega \text{ cm}^2$
Initial	1.34	1.37	2.71
1st remix	1.55	3.12	4.67
2nd remix	1.55	3.77	5.32
3rd remix	1.48	3.93	5.41
4th remix	1.52	3.96	5.48
5th remix	1.52	3.96	5.48
New electrolyte	1.47	4.34	5.80

Figure S12: SEM image of the cross-section of the interface of polymer-carbon composite bipolar plate (BP) and fibres welded graphite felt (GF) for: **a)** fresh HPW electrode assembly and **b)** used HPW GF/BP electrode assembly (after more than 800 cycles). **c)** Detailed on integrated GF fiber in the BP_{ext.} structure via MWW. The sample was cut from the middle of the original electrode. Side cut and polishing was done by a Leica EM FC cryo-ultramicrotome in an axis perpendicular to the fiber-bipolar plate interface. SEM-SE (always left side of the image) and SEM- BE (always right side of the image). **SEM working conditions:** 20 kV; MAG 1380x; VF 500 μm.

Figure S13: Reconstruction of the GF/BP interface from μ CT scans focused on the contact of GF fibres and conductive phase of BP_{ext}. GF fibres are blue and yellow is the conductive phase of BP_{ext}. (i.e. expanded graphite particles). **μ CT working conditions:** accelerating voltage of 55 kV, 2400 images/scan, resolution of 1.091 microns/pixel, an exposure time of 6 s/image.

The results for the GF/BP/GF electrode assembly, including standard deviation, are presented in the figure below (see **Figure S14**). At low compression ratios (CR), the standard deviation is notably higher—particularly for the unbonded assembly—likely due to elevated contact resistance and variability in interface quality. In contrast, the bonded electrode assembly exhibits minimal standard deviation across CR , indicating consistent behaviour.

Figure S14: Development of ASR_{dry} at various CR s of the felt for electrode assemblies: GF/BP_{ext.}/GF GF+BP_{ext.}+GF. Standard deviation is visualized using error bars on the graph. The sign “+” is used for unbonded components.

Techno-economical assessment

First, the scale of production plays a critical role in determining cost efficiency. Obtaining accurate material quotations for large-scale production is challenging without a genuine purchasing intent, and such quotations are typically confidential. We emphasize that a reliable and detailed techno-economic analysis would require access to specific production scales and suitable tooling, which are beyond the scope of this study.

This study primarily demonstrates the feasibility and performance potential of a welded electrode assembly, in which graphite felt (GF) is directly welded onto the carbon-polymer composite plates with high polymer content. The conventional RFB stacks are based on compression/injection-moulded composite bipolar plates with high carbon content, assembled through mechanical compression of GF. Our developed electrode assemblies using exhibit comparable performance to conventional ones, even at significantly lower carbon content in the plate and at reduced relative compression of GF.

To best of our knowledge, no scientific publication has yet directly compared extruded BPs with compression/injection-moulded BPs, either in terms of performance or cost. Only a few extruded BPs (typically highly graphite-filled) are commercially available. According to Minke et al. [1], production cost of compression moulded and injection moulded BPs are similar, while injection moulding is slightly cheaper, therefore we consider injection moulding as a reference production process for comparison. Based on a confidential quotation, the cost reduction for extruded BPs can reach approximately 40%, depending on a production scale.

Considering that polypropylene (PP) is approximately 50% less expensive than graphite, and that our formulation uses a higher PP content, further material cost savings are achievable, despite high cost of CNTs. Additionally, extrusion offers advantages such as lower tooling costs compared to injection moulding, high production rates due to its continuous nature (most important cost/reduction for large scale production and integration of secondary operations, such as in-line GF welding [2]). As a secondary operation we can think about using Mayer machines or microwave welding, which would further reduce assembly costs. While the proposed strategy introduces some additional costs related to the welding, these are likely to be offset by the simplified stack assembly process (less components, decreased error rate). To support our cost analysis, we compared the material requirements using the following assumptions: density $BP_{com.}$ from the producer data sheet, [3], then for the calculation of $BP_{ext.}$ the assumed parameters are summarized in Table S4.

Table S4: Materials savings assumption calculation.

	PP	Graphite	CNT
Density / $kg\ m^{-3}$	900	2260	1600
Normalized cost / Price unit kg^{-1}	0.49	1	20.2

Combining these material savings (see **Table S5**, approx. 30% material cost reduction) with the potential for reduced production and assembly costs, we argue that thinner, highly polymer-filled extruded BPs with welded GF represent a cost-effective alternative to conventionally assembled stacks. Finally, we want to mark out, that detailed techno-economic analysis would require access to specific production scales and suitable tooling, which are beyond the scope of this study.

Table S5: Materials savings calculation and results.

	$BP_{ext.}$	$BP_{com.}$
Thickness / mm	1	2
Density / $kg\ m^{-3}$	1696	1800
Areal density / $kg\ m^{-2}$	1.7	3.6
Normalized cost / Price unit m^{-2}	2.33	3.34

References

1. Minke, C., et al., *Cost and performance prospects for composite bipolar plates in fuel cells and redox flow batteries*. Journal of Power Sources, 2016. **305**: p. 182-190.
2. Medical, A. *Injection Molding vs Extrusion: What is the Difference?* [cited 2025 Jul 7]; Available from: <https://arterexmedical.com/extrusion-vs-injection-molding/#ae>.
3. Eisenhuth, G., & Co., KG;. *PPG86 - Technical Data Sheet*. 2024 [cited 2025 May 26]; Available from: <https://eisenhuth.de/wp-content/uploads/2024/01/PPG86-ENGLISH.pdf>.